

Unconventional Methods for Proving Traditional Inequalities and Applying Them to Extremal Problems

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Abstract: This article will discuss one method of proving inequalities related to Chebyshev's inequality. This method lifts the curtain for students that separates school mathematics from modern mathematics. Its unusualness and beauty contribute to increased interest in mathematics and although the method is quite abstract, it does not require difficulty to understand.

Key words: Monotonic sequence, anti-monotone sequence, permutation of numbers, Chebyshev inequality.

Introduction

Let's start with basic concept-monotonous sequences. First, consider sequences consisting of two numbers: (x_1, x_2) and (y_1, y_2) . Let's write them in the form of a table $\begin{pmatrix} x_1 & x_2 \\ y_1 & y_2 \end{pmatrix}$. These sequences are called monotonic if the numbers x_1, x_2 is above the largest of the numbers y_1, y_2 .

Let us introduce a notation convenient for further discussion:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 \\ y_1 & y_2 \end{bmatrix} = x_1y_1 + x_2y_2$$

Lemma-1. Let (x_1, x_2) , (y_1, y_2) be monotonic sequences. Then

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 \\ y_1 & y_2 \end{bmatrix} \geq \begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 \\ y_2 & y_1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Really,

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 \\ y_1 & y_2 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 \\ y_2 & y_1 \end{bmatrix} = x_1y_1 + x_2y_2 - x_1y_2 - x_2y_1 = (x_1 - x_2)(y_1 - y_2).$$

Since the sequences $x_1 - x_2$ and $y_1 - y_2$ have the same sign. That's why

$$(x_1 - x_2)(y_1 - y_2) \geq 0.$$

Example - 1. Let x, y be positive real numbers, then prove

$$x^3 + y^3 \geq x^2y + y^2x.$$

Let us note first of all that

$$x^3 + y^3 = \begin{bmatrix} x & y \\ x^2 & y^2 \end{bmatrix}, x^2y + y^2x = \begin{bmatrix} x & y \\ y^2 & x^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

And since the sequences $(x, y), (x^2, y^2)$ are monotonic, then

$$\begin{bmatrix} x & y \\ x^2 & y^2 \end{bmatrix} \geq \begin{bmatrix} x & y \\ y^2 & x^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Example - 2. Prove the inequality

$$x^4 + y^4 \leq \frac{x^6}{y^2} + \frac{y^6}{x^2},$$

if x, y are non-zero real numbers.

We have:

$$x^4 + y^4 = \begin{bmatrix} x^6 & y^6 \\ \frac{1}{x^2} & \frac{1}{y^2} \end{bmatrix}, \frac{x^6}{y^2} + \frac{y^6}{x^2} = \begin{bmatrix} x^6 & y^6 \\ \frac{1}{y^2} & \frac{1}{x^2} \end{bmatrix}$$

Noticing now that the sequences $(x^6, y^6), (\frac{1}{y^2}, \frac{1}{x^2})$ are monotone, we obtain this inequality.

Example - 3. Prof the inequality

$$\frac{1}{x^3} + \frac{1}{y^3} \leq \frac{1}{x^3} \sqrt{\frac{y}{x}} + \frac{1}{y^3} \sqrt{\frac{x}{y}}$$

if x, y are positive real numbers.

It's clear that

$$\frac{1}{x^3} + \frac{1}{y^3} = \begin{bmatrix} \sqrt{x} & \sqrt{y} \\ \frac{1}{y^3 \sqrt{x}} & \frac{1}{x^3 \sqrt{y}} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{1}{x^3} \sqrt{\frac{y}{x}} + \frac{1}{y^3} \sqrt{\frac{x}{y}} = \begin{bmatrix} \sqrt{x} & \sqrt{y} \\ \frac{1}{y^3 \sqrt{y}} & \frac{1}{x^3 \sqrt{x}} \end{bmatrix}$$

Moreover, the sequences (\sqrt{x}, \sqrt{y}) and $(\frac{1}{y^3 \sqrt{y}}, \frac{1}{x^3 \sqrt{x}})$ are monotonic.

Now consider sequences consisting of three numbers:

(x_1, x_2, x_3) and (y_1, y_2, y_3)

Let's write them in the form of a table

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & x_3 \\ y_1 & y_2 & y_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

These sequences are called monotonic if the largest number x_1, x_2, x_3 is above the largest number y_1, y_2, y_3 , and the second largest number x_1, x_2, x_3 is above the second largest number y_1, y_2, y_3 .

Let us introduce the notation:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & x_3 \\ y_1 & y_2 & y_3 \end{bmatrix} = x_1 y_1 + x_2 y_2 + x_3 y_3$$

Lemma-2. Let $(x_1, x_2, x_3), (y_1, y_2, y_3)$ be monotonic sequences and (y'_1, y'_2, y'_3) permutations of numbers (y_1, y_2, y_3) .

Then

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & x_3 \\ y_1 & y_2 & y_3 \end{bmatrix} \geq \begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & x_3 \\ y'_1 & y'_2 & y'_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

Consider six numbers of the form

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & x_3 \\ y'_1 & y'_2 & y'_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

We must prove that the maximum among them is the number

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & x_3 \\ y_1 & y_2 & y_3 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Indeed, if the sequence (y'_1, y'_2, y'_3) differs from (x_1, x_2, x_3) then there is a pair of numbers $k_1 \ell$ such that (x_k, x_ℓ) and (y_k, y_ℓ) are not monotonic ($1 \leq k < \ell \leq 3$).

This means that by swapping the numbers y'_k and y'_ℓ , we will increase the sum

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_k & x_\ell \\ y'_k & y'_\ell \end{bmatrix}, \text{ and therefore the entire sum } \begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & x_3 \\ y'_1 & y'_2 & y'_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

Example - 4. Prove that if x, y, z are positive numbers, then

$$x^3 + y^3 + z^3 \geq x^2y + y^2z + z^2x$$

We have

$$x^3 + y^3 + z^3 = \begin{bmatrix} x & y & z \\ x^2 & y^2 & z^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$x^3 + y^3 + z^3 = \begin{bmatrix} x & y & z \\ z^2 & x^2 & y^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

And since the sequences (x, y, z) and (x^3, y^3, z^3) are monotonic, then

$$\begin{bmatrix} x & y & z \\ x^2 & y^2 & z^2 \end{bmatrix} \geq \begin{bmatrix} x & y & z \\ z^2 & x^2 & y^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Example - 5. Prof the inequality

$$\frac{a}{b+c} + \frac{b}{c+a} + \frac{c}{a+b} \geq \frac{3}{2}$$

if a, b, c are positive real numbers.

Because

$$\frac{a}{b+c} + \frac{b}{c+a} + \frac{c}{a+b} = \begin{bmatrix} a & b & c \\ \frac{1}{b+c} & \frac{1}{c+a} & \frac{1}{a+b} \end{bmatrix}$$

and (a, b, c) and $(\frac{1}{b+c}, \frac{1}{c+a}, \frac{1}{a+b})$ one monotonic sequence is

$$\begin{bmatrix} a & b & c \\ \frac{1}{b+c} & \frac{1}{c+a} & \frac{1}{a+b} \end{bmatrix} \geq \begin{bmatrix} a & b & c \\ \frac{1}{c+a} & \frac{1}{a+b} & \frac{1}{b+c} \end{bmatrix}$$

and

$$\begin{bmatrix} a & b & c \\ \frac{1}{b+c} & \frac{1}{c+a} & \frac{1}{a+b} \end{bmatrix} \geq \begin{bmatrix} a & b & c \\ \frac{1}{a+b} & \frac{1}{b+c} & \frac{1}{c+a} \end{bmatrix}$$

Adding these two inequalities, we get

$$2 \left(\frac{a}{b+c} + \frac{b}{c+a} + \frac{c}{a+b} \right) \geq 3$$

Example - 6. If a, b, c are positive real numbers, then prove

$$\frac{a^2}{b+c} + \frac{b^2}{c+a} + \frac{c^2}{a+b} \geq \frac{a+b+c}{2}$$

Because

$$\frac{a^2}{b+c} + \frac{b^2}{c+a} + \frac{c^2}{a+b} = \left[\frac{a^2}{b+c} \quad \frac{b^2}{c+a} \quad \frac{c^2}{a+b} \right]$$

and the sequences (a^2, b^2, c^2) and $(\frac{1}{b+c}, \frac{1}{c+a}, \frac{1}{a+b})$ are monotonic, then

$$\left[\frac{a^2}{b+c} \quad \frac{b^2}{c+a} \quad \frac{c^2}{a+b} \right] \geq \left[\frac{a^2}{c+a} \quad \frac{b^2}{a+b} \quad \frac{c^2}{b+c} \right]$$

and

$$\left[\frac{a^2}{b+c} \quad \frac{b^2}{c+a} \quad \frac{c^2}{a+b} \right] \geq \left[\frac{a^2}{a+b} \quad \frac{b^2}{b+c} \quad \frac{c^2}{c+a} \right]$$

Adding the last two inequalities, we get

$$\begin{aligned} 2 \left(\frac{a^2}{b+c} + \frac{b^2}{c+a} + \frac{c^2}{a+b} \right) &\geq \frac{a^2+b^2}{a+b} + \frac{b^2+c^2}{b+c} + \frac{c^2+a^2}{c+a} \geq \\ &\geq \frac{1}{2}(a+b) + \frac{1}{2}(b+c) + \frac{1}{2}(c+a) = a+b+c \end{aligned}$$

Now consider two sequences consisting of n numbers:

(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) and (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n)

Let's write them in the form of a table

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & \dots & x_n \\ y_1 & y_2 & \dots & y_n \end{pmatrix}$$

This sequences are called monotonic if the largest number x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n is above the largest number y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n , and second largest number x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n is above the second largest number y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n , etc.

Let us introduce notation:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & \dots & x_n \\ y_1 & y_2 & \dots & y_n \end{bmatrix} = x_1y_1 + x_2y_2 + \dots + x_ny_n$$

Lemma-3. Let $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n), (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n)$ - be monotonic sequences and $(y'_1, y'_2, \dots, y'_n)$ be a permutation of the numbers (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n) .

Then

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & \dots & x_n \\ y_1 & y_2 & \dots & y_n \end{bmatrix} \geq \begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & \dots & x_n \\ y'_1 & y'_2 & \dots & y'_n \end{bmatrix}$$

Let's consider all numbers of the form

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & \dots & x_n \\ y'_1 & y'_2 & \dots & y'_n \end{bmatrix}.$$

We need to prove that the maximum number among them is

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & \dots & x_n \\ y_1 & y_2 & \dots & y_n \end{bmatrix}.$$

Indeed, if the sequence $(y'_1, y'_2, \dots, y'_n)$ differs from (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n) then there is a pair of numbers $k_1 \ell$ ($1 \leq k \leq \ell \leq n$) such that the sequence (x_k, x_ℓ) and (y'_k, y'_ℓ) are not monotonic. This means that by interchanging the numbers y'_k and y'_ℓ , we will increase the sum

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_k & x_\ell \\ y'_k & y'_\ell \end{bmatrix}, \text{ and therefore the entire sum } \begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & \dots & x_n \\ y'_1 & y'_2 & \dots & y'_n \end{bmatrix}$$

Example - 7. Prove that if x, y, z, t are positive numbers, then

$$x^3 + y^3 + z^3 + t^3 \geq x^2y + y^2z + z^2x + t^2x$$

Note that

$$x^3 + y^3 + z^3 + t^3 = \begin{bmatrix} x & y & z & t \\ x^2 & y^2 & z^2 & t^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$x^2y + y^2z + z^2t + t^2x = \begin{bmatrix} x & y & z & t \\ t^2 & x^2 & y^2 & z^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

since the sequences (x, y, z, t) and (x^2, y^2, z^2, t^2) are monotone, then the equality is true

$$\begin{bmatrix} x & y & z & t \\ x^2 & y^2 & z^2 & t^2 \end{bmatrix} \geq \begin{bmatrix} x & y & z & t \\ t^2 & x^2 & y^2 & z^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Example - 8. Prove that if x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are positive real numbers whose sum is equal to S , then

$$\frac{x_1}{S - x_1} + \frac{x_2}{S - x_2} + \dots + \frac{x_n}{S - x_n} \geq \frac{n}{n - 1}$$

Since

$$\frac{x_1}{S - x_1} + \frac{x_2}{S - x_2} + \dots + \frac{x_n}{S - x_n} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & \dots & x_n \\ 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 \\ S - x_1 & S - x_2 & \dots & S - x_n \end{bmatrix}$$

and the sequences (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) and $(\frac{1}{S - x_1} + \frac{1}{S - x_2} + \dots + \frac{1}{S - x_n})$ are monotone, then the following $n - 1$ inequalities are true:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & \dots & x_n \\ 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 \\ S - x_1 & S - x_2 & \dots & S - x_n \end{bmatrix} \geq \begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & \dots & x_n \\ 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 \\ S - x_k & S - x_{k+1} & \dots & S - x_{k-1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (k = 2, 3, \dots, n).$$

Adding them up, we get what we need.

The following inequality belongs to the great Russian mathematician P.L.Chebyshev.

Lemma-4. Let the sequences (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) and (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n) be monotonic. Then

$$n(x_1y_1 + x_2y_2 + \dots + x_ny_n) \geq (x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n)(y_1 + y_2 + \dots + y_n).$$

By lemma-3, the following n inequalities are true:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & \dots & x_n \\ y_1 & y_2 & \dots & y_n \end{bmatrix} \geq \begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & \dots & x_n \\ y_k & y_{k+1} & \dots & y_{k-1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (k = 2, 3, \dots, n).$$

Adding them up, we get the required.

Example - 9. Given x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are arbitrary real numbers. Prove that

$$n(x_1^2 + x_2^2 + \dots + x_n^2) \geq (x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n)^2$$

The sequences (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) and (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) are monotonic. Therefore, by virtue of Chebyshev's inequality

$$n(x_1^2 + x_2^2 + \dots + x_n^2) \geq (x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n)(x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n) = (x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n)^2$$

Example - 10. Find the largest value of function

$$Z = \frac{x_1^3 + x_2^3 + x_3^3}{x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2}$$

Provided that the positive numbers x_1, x_2, x_3 satisfy the equation $x_1 + x_2 + x_3 = 6$

Solution. Using Chebyshev's inequality for monotone sequences (x_1^2, x_2^2, x_3^2) and (x_1, x_2, x_3) we obtain the inequality

$$3(x_1^3 + x_2^3 + x_3^3) \geq (x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2)(x_1 + x_2 + x_3)$$

$$\frac{x_1^3 + x_2^3 + x_3^3}{x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2} \geq \frac{x_1 + x_2 + x_3}{2} = \frac{6}{2} = 3$$

Means $Z_{min} = 3$

Example - 11. let a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n be positive real numbers. Then prove that

$$\frac{a_1}{a_2} + \frac{a_2}{a_3} + \dots + \frac{a_n}{a_1} \geq n$$

Solution. As usual, let's start by noting the validity of the following equalities:

$$\frac{a_1}{a_2} + \frac{a_2}{a_3} + \dots + \frac{a_n}{a_1} = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 & a_2 & \dots & a_n \\ \frac{1}{a_2} & \frac{1}{a_3} & \dots & \frac{1}{a_1} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$n = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 & a_2 & \dots & a_n \\ \frac{1}{a_2} & \frac{1}{a_3} & \dots & \frac{1}{a_1} \end{bmatrix}$$

But, unfortunately, the sequences (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) and $(\frac{1}{a_1}, \frac{1}{a_2}, \dots, \frac{1}{a_n})$ are not monotonic, and therefore we cannot use Lemma-3. However, these sequences are anti-monotonic: the numbers in the sequences are arranged in reverse order-the largest corresponds to the smallest, the second largest corresponds to the penultimate largest, etc. and from anti-monotonic sequences it is easy to make monotonous ones by taking all the numbers of the second sequence with a minus sign. In this case, the sequences (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) and $(-\frac{1}{a_1}, -\frac{1}{a_2}, \dots, -\frac{1}{a_n})$.

That's why

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_1 & a_2 & \dots & a_n \\ -\frac{1}{a_1} & -\frac{1}{a_2} & \dots & -\frac{1}{a_n} \end{bmatrix} \geq \begin{bmatrix} a_1 & a_2 & \dots & a_n \\ -\frac{1}{a_2} & -\frac{1}{a_3} & \dots & -\frac{1}{a_1} \end{bmatrix}$$

Hence the desired equality follows.

Example - 12. Given: a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n be positive real numbers. Prove that

$$\frac{a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_n}{n} \geq \left(\frac{a_1^{-2} + a_2^{-2} + \dots + a_n^{-2}}{n} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$$

Let us rewrite this inequality in the form

$$(a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_n)^2 \left(\frac{1}{a_1^2} + \frac{1}{a_2^2} + \dots + \frac{1}{a_n^2} \right) \geq n^3$$

Because

$$\frac{1}{a_1^2} + \frac{1}{a_2^2} + \dots + \frac{1}{a_n^2} \geq \frac{1}{n} \left(\frac{1}{a_1} + \frac{1}{a_2} + \dots + \frac{1}{a_n} \right)^2$$

That

$$(a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_n)^2 \left(\frac{1}{a_1^2} + \frac{1}{a_2^2} + \dots + \frac{1}{a_n^2} \right) \geq \frac{1}{n} \left((a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_n) \left(\frac{1}{a_1} + \frac{1}{a_2} + \dots + \frac{1}{a_n} \right) \right)^2$$

$$\geq \frac{1}{n} \cdot n^4 = n^3$$

Example - 13. Given x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are positive real numbers whose sum is equal to One. Find the smallest value of an expression

$$\frac{x_1}{\sqrt{1-x_1}} + \frac{x_2}{\sqrt{1-x_2}} + \dots + \frac{x_n}{\sqrt{1-x_n}} \rightarrow \min$$

Since the sequences (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) and $\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x_1}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x_2}} + \dots + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x_n}} \right)$ are monotonic, then by virtue of Chebyshev's inequality

$$\frac{x_1}{\sqrt{1-x_1}} + \frac{x_2}{\sqrt{1-x_2}} + \dots + \frac{x_n}{\sqrt{1-x_n}} \geq$$

$$\geq \frac{1}{n} (x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x_1}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x_2}} + \dots + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x_n}} \right) =$$

$$= \frac{1}{n} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x_1}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x_2}} + \dots + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x_n}} \right)$$

By virtue of the previous example we have

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x_1}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x_2}} + \dots + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x_n}} \geq n \left(\frac{1-x_1 + 1-x_2 + \dots + 1-x_n}{n} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} = n \sqrt{\frac{n}{n-1}}$$

So

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x_1}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x_2}} + \dots + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x_n}} \geq \sqrt{\frac{n}{n-1}}$$

Means

$$\min \left\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x_1}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x_2}} + \dots + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x_n}} \right\} = \sqrt{\frac{n}{n-1}}$$

Conclusion

We can give more examples when we consider not two, but a larger number of sequences. And the theorems can be generalized to the case of three or more sequences. The proof of the theorem is quite cumbersome and similar to the proof of the previous theorem. Therefore, we will not bring it.

LITERATURE

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